

Oxidative degradation of antibacterial drug, methylparaben, by Mn^{VII} in perchloric acid medium : A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Abstract : Kinetic and mechanistic study of oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in acidic medium was carried out spectrophotometrically at 25 °C. The stoichiometric ratio between permanganate and methylparaben was found to be 2 : 2. The results have shown that the reaction was first-order with respect to permanganate concentrations and has less than unit order with respect to methylparaben. As the concentration of perchloric acid increases, the rate of reaction also increases. The order with respect to acid concentration was found to be fractional. The oxidation products were identified by spectral studies. The effect of ionic strength, dielectric constant and initially added product were studied on the rate of reaction. A suitable mechanism was proposed on the basis of experimental results. Methylparaben binds to permanganate to form a complex that subsequently decomposes to the products. The reactions were carried out at different temperatures allowing the determination of the activation parameters with respect to slow step by Arrhenius equation and thermodynamic quantities with respect to equilibrium steps by van't Hoff plot of the proposed mechanism.

Keywords : Permanganate, methylparaben, kinetics, oxidation.

Introduction

Potassium permanganate is widely used as an oxidizing agent in both synthetic and analytical chemistry and also as a disinfectant¹. Among the six oxidation states of manganese from II to VII, permanganate, Mn^{VII} , is the most potent oxidation state in both acidic and alkaline media². Oxidation by permanganate ion finds extensive application in organic synthesis³. In general, the reduction¹ of permanganate in acid media goes to Mn^{II} , with reduction potential⁴ of the couple $\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ is 1.51 V. In acid medium, permanganate exists in different forms, namely, HMnO_4 and H_2MnO_4^+ , and depending on the nature of the reductant and oxidant, the oxidation product assigned both inner-sphere and outer-sphere mechanism pathways in their redox reactions^{1,5,6}.

Methylparaben, one of the parabens, is a preservative. It is an antibacterial and fungal agent often used in a variety of cosmetics and personal-care products^{7,8}. Methyl paraben is one of a homologous series of parabens (including methyl, ethyl, butyl, heptyl and benzyl parabens), used singly or in combination to exert the in-

tended antimicrobial affect. Parabens are particularly useful against molds and yeasts⁹. Methylparaben is readily metabolized by common soil bacteria, making it completely biodegradable. The structure of methylparaben is given below :

Methylparaben

The literature survey reveals that there are no reports on the oxidation of methylparaben by any oxidant in acidic medium. In view of the potential pharmaceutical importance of methylparaben the title reaction has been studied.

Results

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The reaction mixtures containing excess of concentra-

tions of MnO_4^- to methylparaben (MP) in the presence of constant amounts of HClO_4 and NaClO_4 were kept in an inert atmosphere for about 8 h. Then, unreacted concentration of Mn^{VII} is determined spectrophotometrically at 526 nm^{10} . It has been found that two moles of MP consumes two moles of Mn^{VII} , (2,2). The observed stoichiometry is represented by eq. (1).

The oxidation products were isolated using the thin-layer chromatography (TLC) separation technique and characterized by physicochemical spectral studies. The reaction products were identified as Mn^{2+} , 4-hydroxybenzoic acid and formic acid. Mn^{2+} was confirmed by UV-Vis spectra and spot test. Product 4-hydroxybenzoic acid was confirmed by IR (KBr) spectra.

Spectroscopic characterisation of the product 4-hydroxy benzoic acid :

Elemental analysis calculated for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_3$ (mol. wt. = 138.12); C, 12.0107; H, 1.00794; O, 15.9994. Found : C, 84.07; H, 6.18; O, 48.27. Melting point of the 4-hydroxy benzoic acid is $214.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, DMSO, at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) : δ 7.780 to 7.757 (2H, d, Ar-H), 6.819 to 6.791 (2H, d, Ar-H), 10.206 (1H, s, -OH), 12.412 (1H, s, -COOH) ppm (Fig. 1). IR spectrum showed acidic C=O stretching peak at $\nu = 1663 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, phenolic -OH stretching peak $\nu = 1588 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and carboxylic acid peak $\nu = 3449 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2). The EI mass spectrum showed an M^+ ion peak at 138 amu clearly confirming 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (Fig. 3). The product formic acid was confirmed by spot test¹¹.

Reaction orders :

The permanganate oxidation of methylparaben in acidic medium proceeds with measurable rates. Hence, the reaction orders have been determined from the slopes of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \log (concentration) plots by varying the concentrations of methylparaben and acid in turn while

keeping others constant.

Effect of permanganate concentration :

The oxidant permanganate concentration was varied in the range of 0.50×10^{-4} to $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, keeping all other conditions constant. At different permanganate concentrations, fairly constant k_{obs} values were obtained (Table 1) indicating a first-order dependence with

respect to the permanganate concentration. This was also confirmed by the linearity of the plots of $\log [\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}]$ versus time up to 80% completion of the reaction (Fig. 4).

Effect of methylparaben concentration :

Further, methylparaben concentration was varied in the range of 0.50×10^{-3} to $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and at constant concentrations of MnO_4^- , HClO_4 and at constant ionic strength. The rate of the reaction increased with increase in concentration of MP (Table 1). The order in the concentration of MP was obtained from the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [\text{MP}]$ and was found to be less than unit order (0.64).

Effect of perchloric acid concentration :

The effect of perchloric acid concentration on the rate of reaction was studied by varying its concentration in the range of 5.0×10^{-2} to $5.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant concentrations of MnO_4^- , MP and at constant ionic strength. The rate of the reaction increased with increase in the concentration of acid (Table 1). The order with respect to H^+ concentration was obtained from the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [\text{H}^+]$ and was found to be less than unit order (0.43).

Effect of ionic strength (I) and dielectric constant (D) concentration :

The ionic strength was varied between 0.20 to 1.20 mol dm^{-3} by varying concentration of NaClO_4 . The addition of NaClO_4 at constant concentrations of reactants

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Fig. 1. NMR spectrum of the product 4-hydroxybenzoic acid.

and other conditions constant, showed that increasing ionic strength had a negligible effect on the rate of reaction. The effect of dielectric constant was studied by varying the acetic acid-water (v/v) content in the reaction mixture from 0% to 40%, with all other conditions being maintained constant. It was found that the rate decreased with decreasing dielectric constant of the reaction medium. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/D$ was linear as shown in Fig. 5.

Effect of initially added products :

The initially added products, *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid and Mn^{II}, did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Polymerization study :

The intervention of free radicals was examined as follows : A known quantity of acrylonitrile scavenger was added to the reaction mixture, which was then kept under an inert atmosphere for 2 h at room temperature. Upon dilution of the reaction mixture with methanol, no precipitate was formed, which indicates the absence of intervention of free radicals in the reaction.

The observed experimental results lead to the following rate law :

$$\text{Rate} = k [\text{MnO}_4]^{1.0} [\text{MEP}]^{0.64} [\text{H}^+]^{0.43}$$

Fig. 2. IR spectrum of the product 4-hydroxybenzoic acid.

Fig. 3. GC-MS spectrum of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid with its molecular ion peak at 138 amu.

Effect of temperature (T) :

The rate of reaction was measured at different temperatures, namely, 15, 25, 35, and 45 °C, with varying concentrations of acid and methylparaben, keeping other conditions constant. The rate of reaction was found to increase with increasing temperature. The rate constant of the slow step (k), the formation constant of K_1 , and the formation constant of complex K_2 in Scheme 1 were obtained from the intercepts and slopes of the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$

versus $1/[H^+]$ (Fig. 6a) and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[MP]$ (Fig. 6b) at four different temperatures. The energy of activation, E_a , was evaluated from the slope of an Arrhenius plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ (Table 2). The enthalpy of activation, ΔH^\ddagger , the entropy of activation, ΔS^\ddagger and the free energy of activation, ΔG^\ddagger were obtained by using the Eyring equation¹² (Table 2). The van't Hoff plot ($\log K_1$ versus $1/T$) was drawn, and the thermodynamic quantities were calculated (Table 2).

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Fig. 4. First order plots of the oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in aqueous acidic medium. $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = (1) 0.5, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.0, (4) 4.0, (5) 5.0, (6) 6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Table 1. Effect of variation of permanganate, methylparaben and HClO₄ concentrations on the oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in perchloric acid solution at 25 °C and $I = 0.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{MnO}_4^-] \times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{MP}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
0.50	5.0	0.2	7.13
1.0	5.0	0.2	7.18
2.0	5.0	0.2	7.13
3.0	5.0	0.2	7.24
4.0	5.0	0.2	7.32
5.0	5.0	0.2	7.12
2.0	0.5	0.2	1.39
2.0	1.0	0.2	2.78
2.0	2.0	0.2	4.71
2.0	3.0	0.2	5.73
2.0	4.0	0.2	6.42
2.0	5.0	0.2	7.13
2.0	5.0	0.05	4.21
2.0	5.0	0.1	5.21
2.0	5.0	0.2	7.13
2.0	5.0	0.3	9.63
2.0	5.0	0.4	12.6
2.0	5.0	0.5	14.2

Discussion

Permanganate ion, MnO_4^- , is a powerful oxidizing agent in acid medium. The stable oxidation product of MnO_4^- in acid medium is Mn^{II} . The spectral changes during the reaction are shown in Fig. 7. A literature sur-

Table 2. Activation parameters and thermodynamic quantities for the oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in aqueous acid medium with respect to the slow step of Scheme 1

(a) Effect of temperature and activation parameters :

Temp. (K)	$k \times 10^2$ (s ⁻¹)	Parameters	Values
288	0.99	E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	40 ± 3
298	1.54	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	37 ± 3
308	2.96	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-155 ± 5
318	4.52	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	83 ± 4
		log A	5.1 ± 0.02

(b) Effect of temperature on K_1 and K_2 :

Temp. (K)	$K_1 \times 10^1$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$K_2 \times 10^{-3}$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)
288	5.39	2.96
289	3.69	5.39
308	1.77	7.47
318	1.36	13.06

(c) Thermodynamic quantities for first (K_1) and second (K_2) equilibrium steps of Scheme 1 :

Thermodynamic quantities	K_1	K_2
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-24	18
ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-76	116
ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-0.5	-17

vey indicated that Mn^{IV} ions absorb¹³ at 418 nm. Fig. 7 shows a lack of spectral change at this wavelength range, which means that MnO_2 is not a reaction product. The reaction between methylparaben and MnO_4^- has a stoichiometry 2 : 2 with a first-order dependence on the MnO_4^- concentration and less-than-unity orders in both the MP

Fig. 5. Effect of dielectric constant (D) on the oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in aqueous acidic medium at 25 °C.

Fig. 6. Verification of rate law (7), in the form of an eq. (6), for the oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in perchlorate solution. Plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus (a) $1/[\text{H}^+]$ and (b) $1/[\text{MP}]$ at different temperatures.

and HClO_4 concentrations. The fact that Mn^{II} is the reduced product of Mn^{VII} in the reaction might indicate that methylparaben shows a strong reducing character in HClO_4 medium.

In view of the experimental observations, a reasonable reaction mechanism can be proposed in which all of

Fig. 7. Spectral changes during the oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in perchloric acid solutions at 25 °C. Conditions $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{MP}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.2$, and $I = 0.6/\text{mol dm}^{-3}$.

the observed orders with respect to the concentrations of constituents, permanganate, methylparaben, and H^+ , can be well accommodated. The active species of permanganate, HMnO_4 , is formed in a prior equilibrium step, which reacts with methylparaben in the second equilibrium step to form complex (C). In the rate determining step complex reduces to methylparaben cation and Mn^{V} species. In the further fast step methylparaben cation hydrolysis to form hydroxymethyl 4-hydroxybenzoate, which is reduced in the next fast step to form oxidation products 4-hydroxybenzoic acid and formaldehyde. In the further fast step formaldehyde react with Mn^{V} , to form oxidised product of formic acid and Mn^{III} species¹⁴. In the last step another mole of permanganate and methylparaben reacts to form same oxidised products. In the next step two moles of Mn^{III} species reduced to form Mn^{II} species¹. The mechanism is represented in the form of Scheme 1.

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Scheme 1

From Scheme 1 the rate law (6) can be derived as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = k [\text{Complex}] \quad (2)$$

But, total permanganate concentration can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} &= kK_2[\text{HMnO}_4] [\text{MP}] \\ [\text{MnO}_4^-]_t &= [\text{MnO}_4^-]_f + [\text{HMnO}_4] + [\text{Complex}] \\ &= [\text{MnO}_4^-]_f + K_1[\text{MnO}_4^-]_f [\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + K_2[\text{MP}] [\text{HMnO}_4] \\ &= [\text{MnO}_4^-]_f + K_1[\text{MnO}_4^-]_f [\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + K_1K_2[\text{MnO}_4^-]_f [\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}] \\ &= [\text{MnO}_4^-]_f \{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-]_f = \frac{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_t}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]} \quad (3)$$

where subscripts t and f stands for total and free MnO_4^- concentrations respectively,

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{MP}]_t &= [\text{MP}]_f + [\text{Complex}] \\ &= [\text{MP}]_f + K_2[\text{MP}]_f + [\text{HMnO}_4] \\ &= [\text{MP}]_f \{1 + K_2[\text{HMnO}_4]\} \end{aligned}$$

$$[\text{MP}]_f = \frac{[\text{MP}]_t}{1 + K_2[\text{HMnO}_4]}$$

$$[\text{MP}]_f = [\text{MP}]_t \quad (4)$$

Because, $K_2 [\text{HMnO}_4] \ll 1$ due to low $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ used in the experiment and,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{H}^+]_t &= [\text{H}^+]_f + [\text{HMnO}_4] \\ &= [\text{H}^+]_f + K_1[\text{HMnO}_4] [\text{H}^+]_f \\ &= [\text{H}^+]_f \{1 + [\text{MnO}_4^-]\} \end{aligned}$$

$$[\text{H}^+]_t = [\text{H}^+]_f \quad (5)$$

Eqs. (3), (4) and (5) are substituted in eq. (2) we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{MnO}_4^-] [\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]} &= k_{\text{obs}} \\ &= \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

The rate law (6) can be rearranged to eq. (7) which is suitable for verification

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} &= \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MP}]} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{kK_2[\text{MP}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

According to eq. (7), plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{MP}]$ should be linear, and are found to be so (Fig. 6a and 6b). From the slopes and intercepts of these plots, the values of k , K_1 and K_2 at 25 °C were obtained as $1.54 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $3.69 \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, and $5.39 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. The value of K_1 is in good agreement with earlier work¹⁵. The modest activation energy and sizeable entropy of activation support a complex transition state in the reaction. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are both favourable for electrontransfer processes¹⁶. The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates that the complex is more ordered than the reactants. The high negative entropy of activation observed in the decomposition of the intermediate complex is in accordance with the propositions suggested for oxidation reactions of an inner-sphere nature¹⁷.

Conclusions

The oxidation of methylparaben by permanganate in aqueous acidic media was investigated. The observed stoichiometry indicates that, the oxidation of two moles of methylparaben requires two moles of permanganate. Based on the experimental observations, a mechanism was proposed via the formation of an intermediate complex between methylparaben and permanganate. The proposed mechanism involves the rate constant of the slow step and other equilibrium constants involved in the mechanism are evaluated, and activation parameters with respect to the slow step of the reaction were computed.

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Oxidation presumably occurs via an inner-sphere mechanism. The overall mechanistic sequence described here is consistent with products (*p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, formic acid and Mn^{II}), mechanistic, and kinetic studies.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade, and doubly distilled water was used throughout this work. An aqueous solution of methylparaben (MP) (Himedia Pvt. Ltd.), the purity of the drug was checked by comparing its IR spectrum and melting point. Permanganate stock solution was obtained by dissolving potassium permanganate (Glaxo, AnalaR) in water and standardized by titrating against oxalic acid¹⁸. Freshly prepared and standardized permanganate solutions were always used in the kinetics experiments. Manganese(II) solution was prepared by dissolving manganese sulfate (AR) in water. Perchloric acid (Glaxo, Excelar) and sodium perchlorate were used to provide the required acidity and ionic strength, respectively.

Kinetic studies :

All kinetics was followed under pseudo-first order conditions, where the concentration of methylparaben was much greater than that of permanganate at 25 °C (unless otherwise specified) and at a constant ionic strength of 0.60 mol dm⁻³. The reaction was initiated by mixing thermally equilibrated solutions of permanganate and methylparaben that also contained the required concentrations of HClO₄ and NaClO₄. The progress of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 526 nm as a function of time by monitoring the decrease in the absorbance of permanganate in a 1-cm cell placed in the thermostatted compartment of a Varian CARY 50 Bio UV-visible spectrophotometer. The molar absorptivity index of permanganate at 526 nm was found to be $\epsilon = 2348 \pm 50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} were evaluated from the plots of $\log [\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}]$ versus time. The plots in all cases were linear over 80% completion of the reaction (Fig. 4). The k_{obs} values were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$ and are the average of minimum three sets of kinetic runs (Table 1).

Instruments used :

(i) For kinetic measurements, a Peltier Accessory (tem-

perature control) attached to Varian CARY 50 Bio UV-visible spectrophotometer (Varian, Victoria-3170, Australia) connected to a rapid kinetic accessory (HI-TECH SFA-12, UK) was used.

(ii) For product analysis, a QP-2010S Shimadzu gas chromatograph mass spectrometer, Nicolet 5700-FT-IR spectrometer (Thermo, USA), 500 MHz ¹H NMR spectrophotometer (Bruker, Switzerland), Thermo Finnigan FLASH EA112. CHNS analyses were used.

(iii) For pH measurements ELICO pH meter model LI 120 was used.

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